

Orientation Errors in Two-Phase Toroidal Magnetic Flux-Gates.

Richard LAO

Port Angeles, Washington, U.S.A.

Abstract

Mathematical equations are derived which determine the 3D alignment errors and secondary winding non-orthogonality of a two-phase toroidal magnetic flux-gate. The flux-gate is installed in its case or pendulously suspended from a Hooke's joint and measurements are conducted on a levelled test stand using only the local geomagnetic field. Derived equations predict the magnetic azimuth or co-azimuth based upon these measured voltages corrected for the alignment and winding non-orthogonality errors.

2019 October 30. RicLAO

DOI 10.5281/zenodo.3523424

Orcid Identifier: <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2575-7803>

1 Two Phase Toroidal Magnetic Flux-Gates

A two-phase toroidal magnetic flux-gate has a primary coil toroidally wound uniformly around the entire high permeability core. Typically two pairs of secondary coils are wound atop the primary coil. These provide the "sine" and "cosine" orthogonal outputs of the magnetic flux-gate. Each secondary coil is uniformly wound on a 90° sector of the core accompanied by a matching companion coil, also occupying a 90° sector, on the other side of the core. The two secondary coils of each pair are electrically connected in series. Thus, two A.C. output signals are available for processing by the associated synchronous demodulators and amplifiers to generate the D.C. output voltages, which we shall designate as MX and MY .

Ideally, if the flux-gate were then rotated around an axis normal to the toroid equatorial plane, and if a magnetic field lying in that plane and pointing to the center of the toroid were present, then the voltage outputs of the amplifiers would vary as the sine and cosine of the rotation angle; that is, $MX \propto \cos \alpha$ and $MY \propto -\sin \alpha$,

where α is the aforementioned rotation angle¹. The toroid equatorial plane referred to above is the plane occupied by the core laminations.

However in manufacture, it is difficult to establish orthogonality between the two pairs of flux-gate secondary windings. For example, the angle between the two windings may be 88° . Consequently (as we shall show), the output voltages will be of the form $MX(\alpha) = a_1 + A_1 \cos \alpha + B_1 \sin \alpha$ and $MY(\alpha) = a_2 + A_2 \cos \alpha + B_2 \sin \alpha$, where $a_1, A_1, B_1, a_2, A_2, B_2$ are constants. Moreover, for use in a magnetic compass, the flux-gate toroid may be pendulously suspended from a Hooke's joint or other mechanical suspension so as to maintain it in the horizontal plane.

In the following derivations we consider how to determine from measurements, what is the orientation, in terms of the Euler angles θ, ϕ, ψ of a toroidal magnetic flux-detector in its case or housing. The Euler angles indicate the 3 dimensional orientation of the orthogonal axes (u, v, w) of the flux-gate toroid relative to the body axes (x, y, z) of the sensor package. The phrases "flux detector" and "flux-gate" are used interchangeably in this paper.

All angles $\theta, \phi, \psi, \delta$ are measured in the standard manner in mathematics, increasing positively in the sense of a right hand screw.

Figure 1: Toroidal Flux-Gate Coordinates.

¹Initially, angles will be measured in standard mathematical format, to be later augmented by the same angles rendered in navigational format.

In this paper we consider only toroidal flux-gates. For a toroidal two-axis (i.e., two phase) magnetic sensor, both sensors lie in one plane, which we call the ψ -plane, and the number of angle variables required to completely specify the orientation of the two axes, the u -axis and the v -axis is 4: θ , ϕ , ψ and δ . **A salient feature of the two-axis toroidal magnetic flux-gate that distinguishes it from one constructed from two discrete sensors is that in the toroid, the magnetic axes u and v lie in virtually the same plane, the ψ -plane.**

Due to difficulties in achieving precisely oriented secondary coil windings, the angle between the u -axis and the v -axis may not be exactly 90° but rather δ ; that is, these axes are non-orthogonal.

The orientation of the non-orthogonal sensor coordinate system (u, v, w) relative to the laboratory space-axes N, W, V is given by modified Euler rotations, the Euler rotation $E(\theta, \phi, \psi)$ followed by a $M(\delta)$ transformation; that is,

$$\begin{pmatrix} u \\ v \\ w \end{pmatrix} = U(\theta, \phi, \psi, \delta) \begin{pmatrix} x \\ y \\ z \end{pmatrix} = M(\delta) E(\theta, \phi, \psi) \begin{pmatrix} x \\ y \\ z \end{pmatrix} \quad (1)$$

$$\text{where } M(\delta) = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 \\ \cos \delta & \sin \delta & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix} \text{ and } E(\theta, \phi, \psi) = \begin{pmatrix} E_{11} & E_{12} & E_{13} \\ E_{21} & E_{22} & E_{23} \\ E_{31} & E_{32} & E_{33} \end{pmatrix} \quad (2)$$

$E(\theta, \phi, \psi) = Z(\theta) \cdot X(\phi) \cdot Z(\psi)$ is the Euler angle rotation matrix,
 $U(\theta, \phi, \psi, \delta) = M(\delta) E(\theta, \phi, \psi)$ is the modified Euler angle matrix

$$U(\theta, \phi, \psi, \delta) = Z(\theta) \cdot X(\phi) \cdot Z(\psi) \cdot M(\delta) = Z(\theta) \cdot X(\phi) \cdot [Z(\psi) \cdot M(\delta)] \quad (3)$$

$$\begin{aligned} E(\theta, \phi, \psi) &= \begin{pmatrix} \cos \psi & \sin \psi & 0 \\ -\sin \psi & \cos \psi & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & \cos \phi & \sin \phi \\ 0 & -\sin \phi & \cos \phi \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} \cos \theta & \sin \theta & 0 \\ -\sin \theta & \cos \theta & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix} \\ &= \begin{pmatrix} \cos \theta \cos \psi - \cos \phi \sin \theta \sin \psi & \sin \theta \cos \psi + \cos \theta \cos \phi \sin \psi & \sin \phi \sin \psi \\ -\cos \theta \sin \psi - \cos \phi \cos \psi \sin \theta & -\sin \theta \sin \psi + \cos \theta \cos \phi \cos \psi & \sin \phi \cos \psi \\ \sin \theta \sin \phi & -\cos \theta \sin \phi & \cos \phi \end{pmatrix} \end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

with

$$\begin{aligned} E_{11} &= \cos \theta \cos \psi - \sin \theta \cos \phi \sin \psi \\ E_{12} &= \sin \theta \cos \psi + \cos \theta \cos \phi \sin \psi \\ E_{13} &= \sin \phi \sin \psi \\ E_{21} &= -\cos \theta \sin \psi - \sin \theta \cos \phi \cos \psi \\ E_{22} &= -\sin \theta \sin \psi + \cos \theta \cos \phi \cos \psi \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
E_{23} &= \sin \phi \cos \psi \\
E_{31} &= \sin \theta \sin \phi \\
E_{32} &= -\cos \theta \sin \phi \\
E_{33} &= \cos \phi
\end{aligned}$$

Note: we could have first evaluated $M(\delta)Z(\theta)$ as

$$M(\delta)Z(\psi) = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 \\ \cos \delta & \sin \delta & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} \cos \psi & \sin \psi & 0 \\ -\sin \psi & \cos \psi & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} \cos \psi & \sin \psi & 0 \\ \cos(\psi + \delta) & \sin(\psi + \delta) & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix} \quad (5)$$

and then written

$$U(\theta, \phi, \psi, \delta) = \begin{pmatrix} \cos \psi & \sin \psi & 0 \\ \cos(\psi + \delta) & \sin(\psi + \delta) & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & \cos \phi & \sin \phi \\ 0 & -\sin \phi & \cos \phi \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} \cos \theta & \sin \theta & 0 \\ -\sin \theta & \cos \theta & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix} \quad (6)$$

A few definitions:

N, W, V : The orthogonal space-axis coordinates on the surface of the earth. N and W lie in the local horizontal plane, and V is the local vertical axis. N is positive towards magnetic north, W is positive toward west, and V is positive vertically upward.

u, v, w : Non-orthogonal body-axis coordinates embedded in the flux-gate toroid.

x, y, z : Orthogonal body-axis coordinates embedded in the sensor box or case enveloping the flux-gate toroid. Ideally (with no orthogonality error) $x = u$, $y = v$, $z = w$.

The wound 2-axis magnetic flux-gate toroid may be installed in this package with the intention of having one sensor-axis directed along each of the body-axes. Most often, perhaps, the toroid is not encased and is simply hung from a universal joint. If the sensor package is in the shape of, for example, a rectangular parallelepiped, most likely the sides of the package will have been chosen as the orthogonal body axes. If the sensor package is in the shape of a short circular cylinder, lines will have probably been inscribed on the upper surface to indicate coordinates u and v , with w understood to be normal to the upper surface. The body axes x, y, z are mutually perpendicular and form a right handed coordinate system.

Repeating, *ideally*, the body-axes x, y are the same as the sensor-axes u, v . But ideal situations do not always prevail. The u sensor axis is always the same as the case axis x , but the v sensor axis may not be exactly equal to the case axis y . A small measure of non-orthogonality between the flux-gate secondary coils will occur, because of the difficulty in establishing tight control of the coil winding machine. There will usually be some alignment error, albeit small. In this paper we derive

equations for computing the sensor alignment errors $\theta, \phi, \psi, \delta$ based upon the azimuth table measurements.

1.1 Method of Conducting Measurements

The azimuth table is set up in the horizontal plane on a test stand. This is accomplished with the use of a bull's eye spirit level. Measurements are obtained by rotating the sensor package in the horizontal plane only, the N-W plane which we shall also refer to as the azimuth or co-azimuth plane. The co-azimuth angle indicating direction of the sensor package rotation in the horizontal plane is α .

Consider the static sensitivities of the associated signal conditioner (synchronous demodulator and amplifier). MX is the x-channel DC output voltage, MY is the y-channel DC output voltage. The input voltages to the signal conditioner are from the secondary coils on the u, v sensor axes.

$$l_1 = \frac{MX}{B_u}, \quad l_2 = \frac{MY}{B_v} \quad (7)$$

We attempt to adjust signal conditioner static sensitivities l_1 and l_2 to be equal to one another. These are measured, e.g., in volts/gauss. After measurements are conducted, l_1 and l_2 will then be found to be approximately equal to one another. Their exact values will be computed using equations derived in this paper.

When $\alpha = 0$, the x body-axis is pointed in the same direction as the N space-axis (Magnetic north). As α is increased from 0 to 360° by rotating the sensor package, MX should vary as $\cos \alpha$ if there are no alignment errors. The y body-axis is pointed in the same direction as the W space-axis (west). In this rotation of the sensor package, MY should vary as $-\sin \alpha$ if there are no alignment errors. The x-y body axes form a right handed coordinate system in this configuration. The angle α , the co-azimuth of the body-axis coordinate x , is measured in the co-azimuth plane in the same sense as θ , that is, counter-clockwise from the space-axis N to the body-axis x .

As we shall demonstrate in this paper, due to misalignment of sensor axes in the sensor package, the output voltages from the x-axis sensor and from the y-axis sensor will be of the forms

$$\begin{aligned} MX(\alpha) &= a_1 + A_1 \cos \alpha + B_1 \sin \alpha \\ MY(\alpha) &= a_2 + A_2 \cos \alpha + B_2 \sin \alpha \end{aligned} \quad (8)$$

In this paper, $a_1, a_2, A_1, B_1, A_2, B_2$ will be evaluated in terms of $\theta, \phi, \psi, \delta$. We use plus signs instead of minus signs in front of B_1 and B_2 in the two equations above, because subsequent evaluation of these coefficients involves a numerical integration which most directly proceeds with this format.

1.1.1 Digression on Sensor, Body & Space Axes

We want the body-axes x, y of the sensor package to be identical to the sensor-axes u, v , but due to sensor orientation errors, as we mentioned earlier, the two sets of axes will not exactly coincide, but almost so.

$$\begin{array}{c} \textit{Body-Axes} \\ \textit{Components} \\ \textit{(Box or case)} \end{array} \begin{pmatrix} x \\ y \\ z \end{pmatrix} = \underbrace{E(\alpha, 0, 0)}_{Z(\alpha)} \begin{array}{c} \textit{Space-Axes} \\ \textit{Components} \end{array} \begin{pmatrix} N \\ W \\ V \end{pmatrix} \Rightarrow \begin{array}{c} \textit{Body-Axes} \\ \textit{Components} \\ \textit{(Box or case)} \end{array} \begin{pmatrix} B_x \\ B_y \\ B_z \end{pmatrix} = \underbrace{E(\alpha, 0, 0)}_{Z(\alpha)} \begin{array}{c} \textit{Space-Axes} \\ \textit{Components} \end{array} \begin{pmatrix} B_N \\ B_W \\ B_V \end{pmatrix}$$

Magnetic Dip Angle

$$\mathbf{B} = \begin{pmatrix} B_N \\ 0 \\ B_V \end{pmatrix} = B \begin{pmatrix} \sin \Delta \\ 0 \\ \cos \Delta \end{pmatrix} = B \begin{pmatrix} \cos D \\ 0 \\ -\sin D \end{pmatrix} \quad (9)$$

where D is the magnetic dip angle and Δ is the magnetic co-dip angle.

Magnetic dip angle is the angle at which the local geomagnetic flux-density vector $\mathbf{B}$ points below the local horizontal plane.

Magnetic dip angle is measured positively downward below the horizontal plane and negatively above the horizontal plane. $D \in [-90^\circ, 90^\circ]$.

Δ = Magnetic co-dip angle; $\Delta \in [0, 180^\circ]$. The co-dip angle Δ is the spherical coordinate slant angle of the local geomagnetic flux-density vector $\mathbf{B}$ measured from the zenith.

Magnetic dip angle $D = \Delta - 90^\circ$.

$\cos D = \sin \Delta$, $\sin D = -\cos \Delta$, $\cot D = -\tan \Delta$ and $-\cot \Delta = \tan D$.

In our derivations we may replace terms using Δ by their equivalents using D .

Angle Formats Since our azimuth table most likely has an azimuth circle rather than one scaled for co-azimuth, we will later replace the co-azimuth angle α (standard mathematical angle format) with azimuth angle Z (navigational angle format).

In standard mathematical angle format, co-azimuth α is a positive angle measured CCW from the N axis looking downward onto the horizontal plane. In navigational angle format, azimuth Z is a positive angle measured CW from the N axis looking downward onto the horizontal plane².

$$Z = 360^\circ - \alpha = -\alpha \quad \text{and} \quad \cos Z = \cos \alpha, \quad \sin Z = -\sin \alpha.$$

Based upon this observation, we can simply replace mathematical angles α with navigational angles Z , by a simple change of sign as in the following:

²CW = clockwise, CCW = counter-clockwise.

$$\begin{aligned}
MX(\alpha) &= a_1 + A_1 \cos \alpha + B_1 \sin \alpha &\Rightarrow & MX(Z) = a_1 + A_1 \cos Z - B_1 \sin Z \\
MY(\alpha) &= a_2 + A_2 \cos \alpha + B_2 \sin \alpha &\Rightarrow & MY(Z) = a_2 + A_2 \cos Z - B_2 \sin Z
\end{aligned}$$

$$\underbrace{E(\alpha, 0, 0)}_{Z(\alpha)} \begin{pmatrix} B_N \\ B_W \\ B_V \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} \cos \alpha & \sin \alpha & 0 \\ -\sin \alpha & \cos \alpha & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix} B \begin{pmatrix} \sin \Delta \\ 0 \\ \cos \Delta \end{pmatrix} = B \begin{pmatrix} \sin \Delta \cos \alpha \\ -\sin \Delta \sin \alpha \\ \cos \Delta \end{pmatrix}$$

*Non-orthogonal
Sensor-Axes
Components
(Actual sensor)*

$$\begin{pmatrix} B_u/B \\ B_v/B \\ B_w/B \end{pmatrix} = U(\theta, \phi, \psi, \delta) \begin{pmatrix} \sin \Delta \cos \alpha \\ -\sin \Delta \sin \alpha \\ \cos \Delta \end{pmatrix} \quad (10)$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\text{But } U(\theta, \phi, \psi, \delta) &= M(\delta) E(\theta, \phi, \psi) = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 \\ \cos \delta & \sin \delta & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} E_{11} & E_{12} & E_{13} \\ E_{21} & E_{22} & E_{23} \\ E_{31} & E_{32} & E_{33} \end{pmatrix} \\
&= \begin{pmatrix} E_{11} & E_{12} & E_{13} \\ E_{11} \cos \delta + E_{21} \sin \delta & E_{12} \cos \delta + E_{22} \sin \delta & E_{13} \cos \delta + E_{23} \sin \delta \\ E_{31} & E_{32} & E_{33} \end{pmatrix}
\end{aligned}$$

$$U_{11} = E_{11} = \cos \theta \cos \psi - \sin \theta \cos \phi \sin \psi$$

$$U_{12} = E_{12} = \sin \theta \cos \psi + \cos \theta \cos \phi \sin \psi$$

$$U_{13} = E_{13} = \sin \phi \sin \psi$$

$$U_{21} = E_{11} \cos \delta + E_{21} \sin \delta = \cos \theta \cos(\psi + \delta) - \cos \phi \sin \theta \sin(\psi + \delta)$$

$$U_{22} = E_{12} \cos \delta + E_{22} \sin \delta = \sin \theta \cos(\psi + \delta) + \cos \theta \cos \phi \sin(\psi + \delta)$$

$$U_{23} = E_{13} \cos \delta + E_{23} \sin \delta = \sin \phi \sin(\psi + \delta)$$

$$U_{31} = E_{31} = \sin \theta \sin \phi$$

$$U_{32} = E_{32} = -\cos \theta \sin \phi$$

$$U_{33} = E_{33} = \cos \phi$$

We have not displayed the 3x3 matrix U , because it would not fit on the printed page; rather, we have written out the individual components above.

$$\begin{pmatrix} MX \\ MY \\ MZ \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} l_1 B_u \\ l_2 B_v \\ l_3 B_w \end{pmatrix} = (l_1 \ l_2 \ l_3) U(\theta, \phi, \psi, \delta) B \begin{pmatrix} \sin \Delta \cos \alpha \\ -\sin \Delta \sin \alpha \\ \cos \Delta \end{pmatrix}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
B_u/B &= E_{11} \sin \Delta \cos \alpha + E_{12}(-\sin \Delta \sin \alpha) + E_{13} \cos \Delta \\
&= (\cos \theta \cos \psi - \cos \phi \sin \theta \sin \psi) \sin \Delta \cos \alpha \\
&\quad - (\sin \theta \cos \psi + \cos \theta \cos \phi \sin \psi) \sin \Delta \sin \alpha + \cos \Delta \sin \phi \sin \psi \\
a_1 &= l_1 B E_{13} \cos \Delta = l_1 B \cos \Delta \sin \phi \sin \psi \tag{11}
\end{aligned}$$

$$A_1 = l_1 B E_{11} \sin \Delta = l_1 B (\cos \theta \cos \psi - \cos \phi \sin \theta \sin \psi) \sin \Delta \tag{12}$$

$$B_1 = l_1 B E_{12} \sin \Delta = -l_1 B (\sin \theta \cos \psi + \cos \theta \cos \phi \sin \psi) \sin \Delta \tag{13}$$

Similarly for B_v/B ,

$$\begin{aligned}
B_v/B &= [\cos \theta \cos(\psi + \delta) - \cos \phi \sin \theta \sin(\psi - \delta)] \sin \Delta \cos \alpha \\
&\quad + [\sin \theta \cos(\psi + \delta) + \cos \theta \cos \phi \sin(\psi + \delta)] (-\sin \Delta \sin \alpha) \\
&\quad + [\sin \phi \sin(\psi + \delta)] \cos \Delta \\
&= [(\cos \theta \cos(\psi + \delta) - \cos \phi \sin \theta \sin(\psi + \delta)) \sin \Delta] \cos \alpha \\
&\quad - [(\sin \theta \cos(\psi + \delta) + \cos \theta \cos \phi \sin(\psi + \delta)) \sin \Delta] \sin \alpha \\
&\quad + [\sin \phi \sin(\psi + \delta)] \cos \Delta \\
a_2 &= l_2 B \sin \phi \sin(\psi + \delta) \cos \Delta \tag{14}
\end{aligned}$$

$$A_2 = l_2 B [\cos \theta \cos(\psi + \delta) - \sin \theta \cos \phi \sin(\psi + \delta)] \sin \Delta \tag{15}$$

$$B_2 = -l_2 B [\sin \theta \cos(\psi + \delta) + \cos \theta \cos \phi \sin(\psi + \delta)] \sin \Delta \tag{16}$$

$$A_1 \cos \theta - B_1 \sin \theta = l_1 B \sin \Delta \cos \psi \tag{17}$$

$$A_2 \cos \theta - B_2 \sin \theta = l_2 B \sin \Delta \cos(\psi + \delta) \tag{18}$$

For $\phi \neq 0$,

$$A_1 \sin \theta + B_1 \cos \theta = -l_1 B \sin \Delta \cos \phi \sin \psi = -a_1 \tan \Delta \cot \phi \tag{19}$$

$$A_2 \sin \theta + B_2 \cos \theta = -l_2 B \sin \Delta \cos \phi \sin(\psi + \delta) = -a_2 \tan \Delta \cot \phi \tag{20}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\begin{pmatrix} A_1 & B_1 \\ A_2 & B_2 \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} \sin \theta \\ \cos \theta \end{pmatrix} &= -\tan \Delta \cot \phi \begin{pmatrix} a_1 \\ a_2 \end{pmatrix} \\
\begin{pmatrix} \sin \theta \\ \cos \theta \end{pmatrix} &= -\tan \Delta \cot \phi \begin{pmatrix} A_1 & B_1 \\ A_2 & B_2 \end{pmatrix}^{-1} \begin{pmatrix} a_1 \\ a_2 \end{pmatrix}
\end{aligned}$$

For any non-singular 2x2 matrix, $\begin{pmatrix} a & b \\ c & d \end{pmatrix}^{-1} = \frac{1}{\Delta_1} \begin{pmatrix} d & -b \\ -c & a \end{pmatrix}$, where $\Delta_1 = \det \begin{vmatrix} a & b \\ c & d \end{vmatrix}$.

So $\begin{pmatrix} A_1 & B_1 \\ A_2 & B_2 \end{pmatrix}^{-1} = \frac{1}{A_1B_2 - B_1A_2} \begin{pmatrix} B_2 & -B_1 \\ -A_2 & A_1 \end{pmatrix}$

For $\phi \neq 0$, $\begin{pmatrix} \sin \theta \\ \cos \theta \end{pmatrix} = -\frac{\tan \Delta \cot \phi}{A_1B_2 - B_1A_2} \begin{pmatrix} B_2 & -B_1 \\ -A_2 & A_1 \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} a_1 \\ a_2 \end{pmatrix}$

$\begin{pmatrix} \sin \theta \\ \cos \theta \end{pmatrix} = \frac{\tan \Delta \cot \phi}{A_1B_2 - B_1A_2} \begin{pmatrix} a_2B_1 - a_1B_2 \\ a_1A_2 - a_2A_1 \end{pmatrix} \Rightarrow$

$\sin \theta = \tan \Delta \cot \phi \frac{a_2B_1 - a_1B_2}{A_1B_2 - B_1A_2}$	and	$\cos \theta = \tan \Delta \cot \phi \frac{a_1A_2 - a_2A_1}{A_1B_2 - B_1A_2}$	(21)
---	-----	---	------

$\tan \theta = \frac{\sin \theta}{\cos \theta} = \frac{a_2B_1 - a_1B_2}{a_1A_2 - a_2A_1}$	(22)
---	------

Figure 2: Various Angles on the MFD2 Toroid.

Determining the Angle ϕ

$$\boxed{\sin^2 \theta + \cos^2 \theta \equiv 1 = \tan^2 \Delta \cot^2 \phi \left[\frac{(a_2 B_1 - a_1 B_2)^2 + (a_1 A_2 - a_2 A_1)^2}{(A_1 B_2 - B_1 A_2)^2} \right]}$$

$$\therefore \cot \phi = \pm \frac{A_1 B_2 - B_1 A_2}{\tan \Delta \sqrt{(a_2 B_1 - a_1 B_2)^2 + (a_1 A_2 - a_2 A_1)^2}}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \tan \phi &= \pm \tan \Delta \sqrt{\left(\frac{a_2 B_1 - a_1 B_2}{A_1 B_2 - B_1 A_2} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{a_1 A_2 - a_2 A_1}{A_1 B_2 - B_1 A_2} \right)^2} \\ &= \pm \tan \Delta \frac{\sqrt{(a_2 B_1 - a_1 B_2)^2 + (a_1 A_2 - a_2 A_1)^2}}{A_1 B_2 - B_1 A_2} \end{aligned}$$

$$\phi = \arctan \left[\pm \tan \Delta \frac{\sqrt{(a_2 B_1 - a_1 B_2)^2 + (a_1 A_2 - a_2 A_1)^2}}{A_1 B_2 - B_1 A_2} \right] \quad (23)$$

Use plus tangent.

We see that the denominator $A_1 B_2 - B_1 A_2 \neq 0$

If a_1 and a_2 are simultaneously equal to zero, then $\phi = 0$ or $\phi = 180^\circ$. In a computation, we might obtain a negative angle ϕ . This is a legitimate result of a trigonometric calculation. In using spherical coordinates, we usually restrict ϕ to the domain $[0, 180^\circ]$; however, that does not invalidate the use of a negative value of ϕ .

Determine the Magnetic Static Sensitivities l_1 and l_2 .

$$\begin{aligned} MX(\alpha) &= l_1 B_u = a_1 + A_1 \cos \alpha + B_1 \sin \alpha \\ MY(\alpha) &= l_2 B_v = a_2 + A_2 \cos \alpha + B_2 \sin \alpha \end{aligned}$$

Since $\Delta = D + 90^\circ$, $\sin \Delta = \cos D$, $\cos \Delta = -\sin D$ and $\tan \Delta = -\cot D$.

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Let } C_1 &= \sqrt{A_1^2 + B_1^2} = l_1 B \sin \Delta \sqrt{\cos^2 \phi \sin^2 \psi + \cos^2 \psi} \\ &= l_1 B \cos D \sqrt{\cos^2 \phi \sin^2 \psi + \cos^2 \psi} \end{aligned}$$

$$C_1^2 + a_1^2 \cot^2 D = (l_1 B \cos D)^2 \quad \Rightarrow \quad \boxed{l_1 = \frac{\sqrt{C_1^2 + a_1^2 \cot^2 D}}{B \cos D}} \quad (24)$$

Likewise,

$$C_2^2 + a_2^2 \cot^2 D = (l_2 B \cos D)^2 \quad \Rightarrow \quad \boxed{l_2 = \frac{\sqrt{C_2^2 + a_2^2 \cot^2 D}}{B \cos D}} \quad (25)$$

Determining the Angles ψ and δ We previously derived the following two equations (repeated here),

$$\begin{aligned} A_1 \sin \theta + B_1 \cos \theta &= -l_1 B \sin \Delta \cos \phi \sin \psi \\ A_1 \cos \theta - B_1 \sin \theta &= l_1 B \sin \Delta \cos \psi \end{aligned}$$

$$\sin \psi = -\frac{A_1 \sin \theta + B_1 \cos \theta}{l_1 B \sin \Delta \cos \phi} \quad \text{and} \quad \cos \psi = \frac{A_1 \cos \theta - B_1 \sin \theta}{l_1 B \sin \Delta} \quad (26)$$

From these two equations, we evaluate the angle ψ justified for quadrant. Similarly,

$$\begin{aligned} A_2 \sin \theta + B_2 \cos \theta &= -l_2 B \sin \Delta \cos \phi \sin(\psi + \delta) \\ A_2 \cos \theta - B_2 \sin \theta &= l_2 B \sin \Delta \cos(\psi + \delta) \end{aligned}$$

$$\sin(\psi + \delta) = -\frac{A_2 \sin \theta + B_2 \cos \theta}{l_2 B \sin \Delta \cos \phi} \quad \text{and} \quad \cos(\psi + \delta) = \frac{A_2 \cos \theta - B_2 \sin \theta}{l_2 B \sin \Delta} \quad (27)$$

From these two equations, we evaluate the angle $\psi + \delta$, justified for quadrant.

Note: α is the co-azimuth of body-axis x in the N-W plane and $\alpha + \theta$ is the co-azimuth of sensor-axis u in the N-W plane. On the test stand, data is taken at equal intervals of azimuth $Z = 360^\circ - \alpha$.

$$a_1 = l_1 B \cos \Delta \sin \phi \sin \psi = 0 \quad \text{iff} \quad \phi = 0, \phi = 180^\circ, \psi = 0 \text{ or } \psi = 180^\circ.$$

$$a_2 = l_2 B \sin \phi \sin(\psi + \delta) \cos \Delta = 0 \quad \text{iff} \quad \phi = 0, \phi = 180^\circ, \psi + \delta = 0 \text{ or } \psi + \delta = 180^\circ.$$

$$a_1 = 0 \quad \underline{\text{and}} \quad a_2 = 0 \quad \text{iff} \quad \phi = 0, \phi = 180^\circ.$$

We conclude conversely that $a_1 = 0$ and $a_2 = 0 \Rightarrow \phi = 0$ or $\phi = 180^\circ$.

Computing the Best Fit Equations for MX and MY

Consider a function $y(\theta)$ expanded into a Fourier series:

$$y(\theta) = a_0 + \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} (A_k \cos k \theta + B_k \sin k \theta)$$

In this paper, we express angles in degrees rather than in radians.

$$\frac{\theta}{2\pi} = \frac{\theta_{\text{deg}}}{360} \quad \Rightarrow \quad d\theta = \frac{2\pi}{360} d\theta_{\text{deg}}.$$

After making the radian to degree conversions, we shall drop the "deg." subscript from θ .

$$a_0 = \frac{1}{2\pi} \int_0^{2\pi} y(\theta) d\theta = \frac{1}{360} \int_0^{360} y(\theta) d\theta$$

$$A_k = \frac{1}{\pi} \int_0^{2\pi} y(\theta) \cos k\theta d\theta = \frac{2}{360} \int_0^{360} y(\theta) \cos k\theta d\theta$$

$$B_k = \frac{1}{\pi} \int_0^{2\pi} y(\theta) \sin k\theta d\theta = \frac{2}{360} \int_0^{360} y(\theta) \sin k\theta d\theta$$

Keep in mind that the integral for a_0 has a $\frac{1}{2\pi}$ factor, whereas the integrals for A_k and B_k have a $\frac{1}{\pi}$ factor.

Furthermore, recall that the average value of a function $y(\theta)$ over the interval $[a, b]$ is

$$\bar{y}(\theta) = \frac{1}{b-a} \int_a^b y(\theta) d\theta$$

Thus, the equations for A_k and B_k above express averages.

If we let $y(\theta) \leftarrow MX(\alpha)$ and $y(\theta) \leftarrow MY(\alpha)$ with $a_0 \leftarrow a_1$ and $a_0 \leftarrow a_2$, we can rewrite

$$MX(\alpha) \approx a_1 + \sum_{k=1}^N [A_1(k) \cos k\alpha + B_1(k) \sin k\alpha]$$

$$MY(\alpha) \approx a_2 + \sum_{k=1}^N [A_2(k) \cos k\alpha + B_2(k) \sin k\alpha]$$

We can also write this as

$$MX(\alpha) \approx \sum_{k=0}^N [A_1(k) \cos k\alpha + B_1(k) \sin k\alpha]$$

$$MY(\alpha) \approx \sum_{k=0}^N [A_2(k) \cos k\alpha + B_2(k) \sin k\alpha]$$

with $A_1(0) = a_1$ and $A_2(0) = a_2$

In a sample computer program to be provided, we shall ignore all harmonics except the first ($k = 1$) and write $A_1(1) = A_1$, $B_1(1) = B_1$, $A_2(1) = A_2$, $B_2(1) = B_2$. We can determine these coefficients using numerical integrations, either rectangular, trapezoidal or parabolic (Simpson's Rule). The ignored higher harmonics might be regarded as truncation and round-off errors.

$\theta \leftarrow \theta_k$, $d\theta \leftarrow \Delta\theta = \frac{b-a}{N} = \frac{360-0}{N} = \frac{360}{N}$. The simplest of these is rectangular integration. However, trapezoidal and parabolic numerical integration are more accurate.

Rectangular, $\int_a^b y(\theta)d\theta \approx \Delta\theta \sum_{k=0}^N y_k$, e.g., $\Delta\theta (y_0 + y_1 + y_2 + y_3)$.

Trapezoidal, $\int_a^b y(\theta)d\theta \approx \Delta\theta \sum_{k=0}^N p_k y_k$, e.g., $\Delta\theta (\frac{1}{2}y_0 + y_1 + y_2 + \frac{1}{2}y_3)$
where $p_k = \frac{1}{2}$ if $k = 0$ or N , else $p_k = 1$.

Parabolic, $\int_a^b y(\theta)d\theta \approx \Delta\theta \sum_{k=0}^N p_k y_k$, e.g.,
 $\frac{\Delta\theta}{3} (y_0 + 4y_1 + 2y_2 + 4y_3 + \dots + 4y_{N-2} + 2y_{N-1} + y_N)$,

where $p_k = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } k = 0 \text{ or } N \\ 2 & \text{if } k = 2, 4, 6, 8, \dots, \text{etc. (even numbered } k) \\ 4 & \text{if } k = 1, 3, 5, 7, 9, \dots, \text{etc. (odd numbered } k) \end{cases}$

$$A_k = 2 \frac{1}{360} \int_0^{360} y(\theta) \cos k\theta d\theta \leftarrow \frac{2}{360} \frac{1}{3} \sum_{k=0}^N p_k y(\theta_k) \cos k\theta \left(\frac{360}{N} \right)$$

$$= \frac{2}{3N} \sum_{k=0}^N p_k y(\theta_k) \cos k\theta$$

$$B_k = 2 \frac{1}{360} \int_0^{360} y(\theta) \sin k\theta d\theta \leftarrow \frac{2}{360} \frac{1}{3} \sum_{k=0}^N p_k y(\theta_k) \sin k\theta \left(\frac{360}{N} \right)$$

$$= \frac{2}{3N} \sum_{k=0}^N p_k y(\theta_k) \sin k\theta$$

A sample computer program that computes the parameters $a_1, A_1, B_1, a_2, A_2, B_2$ as a function of measured values of MX and MY is provided in the Appendix.

Computing Azimuth Z from Voltages MX and MY

$MX = MX(\alpha)$ and $MY = MY(\alpha)$ unless otherwise specified.

$$MX(\alpha) = a_1 + A_1 \cos \alpha + B_1 \sin \alpha, \quad MY(\alpha) = a_2 + A_2 \cos \alpha + B_2 \sin \alpha, \quad Z = 360^\circ - \alpha$$

$$\cos Z = \cos(360^\circ - \alpha) = \cos \alpha, \quad \sin Z = \sin(360^\circ - \alpha) = -\sin \alpha$$

Thus, we may also write

$$MX(Z) = a_1 + A_1 \cos Z - B_1 \sin Z, \quad MY(Z) = a_2 + A_2 \cos Z - B_2 \sin Z$$

$$B_2 MX = a_1 B_2 + A_1 B_2 \cos \alpha + B_1 B_2 \sin \alpha$$

$$B_1 MY = a_2 B_1 + A_2 B_1 \cos \alpha + B_1 B_2 \sin \alpha$$

$$B_2 MX - B_1 MY = (a_1 B_2 - a_2 B_1) + (A_1 B_2 - A_2 B_1) \cos \alpha$$

$$\boxed{\cos Z = \cos \alpha = \frac{(B_2 MX - B_1 MY) - (a_1 B_2 - a_2 B_1)}{A_1 B_2 - A_2 B_1}} \quad (28)$$

Similarly,

$$\begin{aligned} A_2 MX &= a_1 A_2 + A_1 A_2 \cos \alpha + B_1 A_2 \sin \alpha \\ A_1 MY &= a_2 A_1 + A_2 A_1 \cos \alpha + A_1 B_2 \sin \alpha \\ A_2 MX - A_1 MY &= (a_1 A_2 - a_2 A_1) + (B_1 A_2 - A_1 B_2) \sin \alpha \end{aligned}$$

$$\boxed{-\sin Z = \sin \alpha = -\frac{(A_2 MX - A_1 MY) - (a_1 A_2 - a_2 A_1)}{A_1 B_2 - B_1 A_2}} \quad (29)$$

If we measure the voltages MX and MY , we then determine the (quadrant justified) azimuth Z using

$$Z = \text{atn2}(\cos Z, \sin Z)$$

Appendix: A Sample Computer Program to Evaluate $a_1, A_1, B_1, a_2, A_2, B_2$

The following program was written and run in TrueBASIC (version 6.007) and might be used as pseudocode for programming in another computer language.

```

print "The name of this TrueBasic source file is Simp1.tru."
! THE AUTHOR ASSUMES NO RESPONSIBILITY FOR ERRORS OR
! OMISSIONS IN THE SOFTWARE OR DOCUMENTATION, AND
! PROVIDES NO GUARANTEES FOR ANY USE BY THE USER.
! USE AT YOUR OWN RISK.
Option nolet
Option angle degrees
Option base 0
dim mx(181), my(181) ! Aliases: MX = mx, MY = my.
! Definitions:
def fnr6(d) = int(d*1000000 + 0.5)/1000000 ! Round off to 6 decimal places.
def fnr4(d) = int(d*10000 + 0.5)/10000 ! Round off to 4 decimal places.
print "Divide the azimuth circle into how many parts, N?"
input prompt "(An even positive integer in [8,180] )": N
print
print "Enter the measured voltages MX(Z) and MY(Z)."
print "MX(Z), MY(Z) and azimuth Z will be converted to MX(alpha), MY(alpha)"
print "and co-azimuth alpha for subsequent evaluation of parameters."
print
for k = 0 to N
  print "k ="; k
  print "MX("; k*360/N; ") ="
  input mx(N - k) ! To convert to co-azimuth values.
  print "MY("; k*360/N; ") ="
  input my(N - k) ! To convert to co-azimuth values.
next k
print "The following data are MX(alpha) and MY(alpha):"

```

```

for k = 0 to N
  print "MX("; k*360/N; ") ="; mx(k); tab(24); "MY("; k*360/N; ") ="; my(k)
next k
print "The MX(alpha) & MY(alpha) above were converted from the MX(Z) &
MY(Z)"
print "that were typed in."
print "A sample was taken every 360/N ="; 360/N; "degrees."
print "The number of samples measured is N + 1 ="; N + 1; "."
print
print "Determine Fourier coefficients based upon MX(k) and MY(k) inputs."
print "Best fit (Simpson's Rule numerical integration):"
! IN: MX(k), MY(k) for k in [0, N].
! OUT: aa1, aa2 A1, B1, A2, B2.
delta = 360/N ! This is the azimuth angle sampling interval (degrees).
S1 = 0 ! Partial Sums
S2 = 0
S3 = 0
S4 = 0
S5 = 0
S6 = 0
for k = 0 to N
  if mod(k,2) = 0 then p = 2 else p = 4
    ! In TrueBasic, mod(x,y) = x mod y = x - y*Int(x/y).
    ! mod(even,2) = 0 and mod(odd,2) = 1.
  if k = 0 or k = N then p = 1
  S1 = S1 + p*mx(k)
  S2 = S2 + p*mx(k)*cos(k*delta)
  S3 = S3 + p*mx(k)*sin(k*delta)
  S4 = S4 + p*my(k)
  S5 = S5 + p*my(k)*cos(k*delta)
  S6 = S6 + p*my(k)*sin(k*delta)
next k
aa1 = S1/(3*N)
A1 = 2*S2/(3*N)
B1 = 2*S3/(3*N)
!
aa2 = S4/(3*N)
A2 = 2*S5/(3*N)
B2 = 2*S6/(3*N)
! End computation of Fourier coefficients.
print "aa1 ="; fnr6(aa1)
print "A1 ="; fnr6(A1)

```

```

print "B1 ="; fnr6(B1)
print "aa2 ="; fnr6(aa2)
print "A2 ="; fnr6(A2)
print "B2 ="; fnr6(B2)
print
print "_____ "
print using "MX(alpha) = +#.#####": aa1;
print using " +#.##### COS(alpha)": A1;
print using " +#.##### SIN(alpha)": B1
print using "MY(alpha) = +#.#####": aa2;
print using " +#.##### COS(alpha)": A2;
print using " +#.##### SIN(alpha)": B2
print "_____ "
print using "MX(Z) = +#.#####": aa1;
print using " +#.##### COS(Z)": A1;
print using " +#.##### SIN(Z)": -B1
print using "MY(Z) = +#.#####": aa2;
print using " +#.##### COS(Z)": A2;
print using " +#.##### SIN(Z)": -B2
print "_____ "
print
print "End of program."
End

```

■ End